

ANALYSIS OF THE MIXED-MODE END LOAD SPLIT DELAMINATION TEST

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SUMMARY: Composite delaminations are commonly analysed using the double cantilever beam test for mode I, the end-notched flexure test or the end load split test for mode II and the mixed-mode bending test for mixed-mode. For all these tests, the mode mix remains constant and does not vary with the crack length. However, in the mixed-mode end load split test (MMELS), the delamination propagates under a varying mode mix that depends on the crack extension, which is a more realistic scenario. The MMELS test has been previously analysed by different researchers but the resulting expressions are not equivalent. A more accurate alternative analysis of the test, based on the finite element method and the virtual crack closure technique, is used in the present work for comparison. The results are compared to the predictions of the approaches in the literature and significant findings are found for materials characterization using the MMELS test.

KEYWORDS: MMELS test, variable mixed-mode, delamination, composite laminates.

INTRODUCTION

Failure of composite laminates involves different damage mechanisms that result in the degradation of the material. One of the most important damage mechanisms, commonly referred to as delamination, is caused by the debonding of two adjacent plies of the laminate. In aeronautical applications, composite plates are sensitive to impact, and delamination occurs readily in composite laminates on impact. If the composite structure is subsequently loaded in compression, delaminations are likely to grow in varying crack propagation mode and eventually cause structural failure by buckling [1]. Many composite components have curved shapes, tapered thickness and plies with different orientations, which will also make the delamination grow with a mode mix that depends on the extent of the crack. Therefore, delaminations in composite laminates generally grow under varying mixed-mode conditions.

Delaminations are commonly studied in laboratory conditions using essentially unidirectional fibre reinforced polymer laminates. These laminates are generally tested in mode I by using the double cantilever beam test, in mode II by using the end-notched flexure test or the end load split test and mixed-mode I/II by using the mixed-mode bending test. The mode III contribution in delamination growth of composite laminates is usually not considered. For all these tests, the ratio between mode I and mode II, mixed-mode, remains constant and does not vary with the crack extension. In order to obtain a complete characterization of the delamination growth in composite laminates, the study of the propagation of interlaminar

cracks under varying mixed-mode conditions is also required. Therefore, the tests mentioned above should be complemented by using a delamination test where the mode mix continuously varies with the crack extension. This is the case of the mixed-mode end load split (MMELS) delamination test. This test is similar to previous tests but in this case the delamination propagates under a varying mode mix that depends on the crack length, a , which is a more realistic scenario.

The MMELS test has been previously analysed by different researchers in different studies. Among these, the approaches proposed by Hashemi *et al.* [2], Kinloch *et al.* [3] and Bao *et al.* [4] can be considered as the more relevant. The first two studies are based on the beam theory expressions formulated by Williams [5] and propose a series of analytical expressions for the characterization of the test. The latter, is based on the orthotropic rescaling technique [6] in combination with finite element results. In this case, the expressions proposed for the characterization of the MMELS test are obtained after a curve fit procedure of the finite element results. In the present study, the crack tip element analysis in combination with the non-singular field approach proposed by Davidson *et al* [7], has been also considered for obtaining the energy release rate components and modelling the MMELS test. The resulting expressions for the calculation of the energy release rate components in the MMELS test of these three approaches are not equivalent. In some cases, the difference between the predictions can be up to 50 times. In order to elucidate which one of the three approaches can be taken as the most accurate for modelling the MMELS test, a more accurate alternative analysis of the MMELS test is used in the present work for comparison. The analysis is carried out based on the finite element method and the virtual crack closure technique [8]. Different specimens are modelled and the results compared to the predictions of the previous approaches. Significant findings are found for precise materials characterization using the MMELS test.

THE MMELS TEST

The MMELS test is a variation of the ELS test where the interlaminar crack in a beam-type specimen is forced to propagate under mixed-mode. As in the ELS test, only one of the beams of the specimen is loaded in the MMELS test (see Fig. 1). In this way, a pulling force is applied to one of the specimen beams while the other remains unloaded. This particular loading causes the two specimen beams to deflect in a different way depending on the crack length, a . For short crack lengths, the deflection of both arms is almost similar (see Fig. 1 (a)), whilst for larger values of a the unloaded beam remains almost without deflection (see Fig. 1 (b)). The peculiarity of the MMELS test is that the mode mix is continuously varying as a function of the delamination length, as it will be demonstrated later on. The variation of the mode mix is more pronounced for short crack lengths whilst an asymptotic value is reached for long delaminations. As this situation is more likely to occur in the delamination process of a real composite structure, the variation of the mode mix with the crack length is more suitable to reproduce real propagation than other mixed-mode tests. In addition, compared to the most used mix-mode test, the MMB test, the way in which the external load is applied to the specimen can be more easily assimilated to a loading situation of a real structure.

Fig. 1: Illustration of the mixed-mode end load split test specimen: (a) for short crack lengths and (b) for long crack lengths

According to some recommendations [3, **Error! Bookmark not defined.**], the MMELS test rig can be slightly modified to avoid the inclusion of axial forces on the beams of the specimen while the applied load is kept in the initial direction (usually in the vertical direction). The alternative test rig proposed by [**Error! Bookmark not defined.**] can be seen in Fig. 2(a), while the alternative proposed by [3] is shown in Fig. 2(b). Both cases consider a fixed loading point and the clamping of the end of the specimen between rollers. In this way, while the specimen is free to move along the horizontal direction, the vertical movement of the clamped end remains restricted and no axial forces are originated. Although both alternatives are very similar, the one proposed by [3] implies the modification of the effective length of the specimen, L , during the test [9]. Consequently, the alternative shown in Fig. 2(a) is believed to be more appropriate to reproduce the interlaminar crack propagation of a real composite structure.

Fig. 2: Alternative MMELS test rigs with sliding clamped end and fixed load point: (a) alternative proposed in [**Error! Bookmark not defined.**] and (b) alternative proposed in [3]

MODELLING OF THE MMELS TEST

The MMELS test has been previously analysed by other researchers. The different works on the subject can be basically grouped in two different approaches. The first approach corresponds to the first order beam theory (BT), including the studies of Hashemi *et al.* [2] and Kinloch *et al.* [3]. The second approach, based on an orthotropic rescaling technique (OR) in combination with finite element results, was proposed by Bao *et al.* [4]. In the present study, the MMELS test is also modelled by means of the crack tip element analysis in combination with the non-singular field approach (CTE/NSF) proposed by Davidson *et al* [7]. A summary of these approaches is included in the following sub-sections for clarity.

In order to establish a comparison between the three approaches, four different specimens are taken into account. The specimens are considered to be cut from unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminates with all the fibres aligned in the direction of the crack growth. The mechanical properties of the unidirectional HTA/6376C carbon/epoxy prepreg are taken as a reference,

which elastic properties of the material are summarised in Table 1 [Error! Bookmark not defined.]. The average thickness of a unidirectional ply is assumed to be the average thickness of the cured plies, 0.13 mm.

Table 1: Elastic properties of the unidirectional HTA/6376C carbon/epoxy prepreg

E_{11} (GPa)	$E_{22} = E_{33}$ (GPa)	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	ν_{23}	$G_{12} = G_{13}$ (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)
120	10.5	0.30	0.51	5.25	3.48

The basic geometric properties of the specimens are given according to a width $b = 20$ mm and an effective length $L = 150$ mm. The four different types of specimens are determined according to the ratio between the thickness of the loaded and unloaded beams of the specimen, *i.e.* $\eta = h_1/h_2$. The thickness of the unloaded specimen beam, h_2 , is fixed to the thickness of 20 unidirectional plies, 2.6 mm. The thickness of the loaded beam of the specimen, h_1 , is chosen in order to achieve the different thickness ratios, η . Without loss of generality, only $\eta \leq 1$ values are considered [4]. In fact, h_1 is set to the thicknesses associated to 5, 10, 15 and 20 plies. Therefore the resulting thickness ratios are $\eta = 0.25$, $\eta = 0.5$, $\eta = 0.75$ and $\eta = 1$. In all cases, it is assumed that a unit external load, P , is applied centred with the specimen beam. In this way, there is no need to consider the correction factors for the shortening of the lever arm due to the rotation of the beam [Error! Bookmark not defined.].

Beam theory (BT)

After the deductions of Williams [5] and Hashemi *et al.* [2], it is possible to determine the energy release rate G of a delamination specimen based on the applied moments at the end of a crack. Fig. 3 shows a composite laminate of thickness $2h$ and width b containing a delamination of length a at a distance h_1 from the top surface. The zoom of the crack tip in the figure shows the applied loads and moments, which are uniform in the width direction. The upper beam is loaded with a moment M_1 , an axial force N_1 and a shear force Q_1 , while the lower beam is loaded with a moment M_2 , an axial force N_2 and a shear force Q_2 . However, in this case the axial forces are zero and, in general, the effect of the shear forces is neglected.

Fig. 3: Delamination geometry and crack tip loaded with axial and shear forces and moments Then, according to the beam theory, the mode I and mode II components of the energy release rate for the MMELS test when only moments are applied can be calculated as follows

$$G_I = \frac{6P^2(a + \chi_I h_1)^2}{b^2 E_{11} h_1^3 (1 + \eta^3)} \quad (1)$$

$$G_{II} = \frac{18P^2(a + \chi_{II} h_1)^2 \eta^4}{b^2 E_{11} h_1^3 (1 + \eta)^2 (1 + \eta^3)} \quad (2)$$

where the parameters χ_I and χ_{II} are the correction crack length factors to take into account that the deflection of the specimen beams is not zero at the crack tip. The expressions for χ_I and χ_{II} can be found elsewhere [3]. The variation of the total energy release rate, taken as $G = G_I + G_{II}$ (mode III is neglected), and the mode mix, G_{II}/G , versus the crack length for the specimens with four different thickness ratios when only moments are taken into account is shown in Fig. 4. In this figure, for each thickness ratio the crack length has been set according to $10\eta \leq a \leq 100$ mm.

Fig. 4: BT variation of G and G_{II}/G versus the a for the MMELS test loaded with moments

Orthotropic rescaling (OR)

Based on an orthotropic rescaling technique [6] in combination with finite element solutions, Bao *et al.* [4] analysed the MMELS test among other composite delamination tests. In their work, Bao and co-workers do not give much information about the details of the finite element simulations. However, for the comparison with the other approaches it will be considered that the external load is applied centred with the beam of the specimen, no axial forces are present and that shear forces are taken into account. In this case, for the MMELS test specimens with $h_1 \leq h_2$, the total and mode I energy release rates are respectively given by

$$G = \frac{6P^2}{b^2 E_{11} h_1^3} \left(1 - \left(1 + \frac{1}{\eta} \right)^{-3} \right) \left(a + Y(1 + F(1 - \eta)) \lambda^{\frac{-1}{4}} h_1 \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

$$G_I = \frac{AP^2}{b^2 E_{11} h_1^3} \left(a + Y_I(1 + F_1(1 - \eta)) \lambda^{\frac{-1}{4}} h_1 \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

where the first term of both equations is determined from the simple beam theory solution, which is the exact asymptote for $a \gg h$, and $\lambda = E_{22}/E_{11}$. The expressions for the empirical factors Y , F , A , Y_I and F_1 can be found in [4]. Since mode III is considered negligible, the mode II energy release rate can be found from the difference of equations (3) and (4). The

variation of G and G_{II}/G versus the crack length according to the orthotropic rescaling approach for the specimens with four different thickness ratios is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: OR variation of G and G_{II}/G versus the crack length for the MMELS test

Crack tip element/non-singular field (CTE/NSF)

The crack tip element analysis in combination with the non-singular field approach proposed by Davidson *et al.* [7] is used in this study to analyse and model the MMELS test. The CTE/NSF approach assumes that the mode mix can be characterized by classical plate theory parameters. Actually, the energy release rate components are obtained through the concentrated crack tip force, N_c , and moment, M_c , which are functions of the applied loads and the material properties and geometry of the specimen (see Fig. 3). The effect of the shear forces is not taken into account in the CTE/NSF approach and in this case the axial forces are set to zero. Then, the mode I and mode II components of the energy release rate can be then obtained as functions of a series of parameters. These parameters only depend on the stiffness matrix of the laminates that define the loaded beam, the unloaded beam and the uncracked region of the specimen. The CTE/NSF equations for the calculation of G_I and G_{II} are given by

$$G_I = \frac{1}{2} \left(-N_c \sqrt{c_1} \sin \Omega + M_c \sqrt{c_2} \cos(\Omega + \Gamma) \right)^2 \quad (5)$$

$$G_{II} = \frac{1}{2} \left(N_c \sqrt{c_1} \cos \Omega + M_c \sqrt{c_2} \sin(\Omega + \Gamma) \right)^2 \quad (6)$$

where the parameters c_1 , c_2 and Γ are determined through the terms of the stiffness matrix of the specimen, and the mode mix parameter, Ω , is obtained by means of experimental data [7]. The variation of G and G_{II}/G versus the crack length according for the CTE/NSF approach for the specimens with four different thickness ratios is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: CTE/NSF variation of G and G_{II}/G versus the crack length for the MMELS test

Comparing the resulting variation of the total energy release rate and mode mix versus crack length for the three approaches (Fig. 4, Fig. 5 and Fig. 6), it can be seen that the total energy release rate predicted by the beam theory and orthotropic rescaling approaches is similar. However, the variation of G with the crack length predicted by the CTE/NSF approach differs from the other two. The variation of G_{II}/G versus a only coincides for the BT and OR approaches when $\eta = 1$. For the rest of the cases, the difference between predicted values can be up to 50 times, even if BT should be an the exact asymptote for the OR. Conversely, no variation of the mode mix with the crack length is predicted by the CTE/NSF approach. Consequently, a more accurate alternative analysis of the MMELS test is carried out to elucidate which of the previous approaches can be taken as a reference.

ALTERNATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE MMELS TEST

The alternative analysis of the MMELS test proposed in this study is based on the finite element method in combination with the virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) [8]. The VCCT has been chosen because it is the most common finite element method for mode mix analysis [7,10]. The analysis is carried out using the commercial MSC-Marc finite element program. The alternative proposed by [Error! Bookmark not defined.] (see Fig. 2(a)) for the MMELS test is modelled using 2-D four-noded plane-stress elements. A schema of one of the MMELS specimens modelled with an effective length $L = 150$ mm and a sliding clamped area of 50 mm is shown in Fig. 7. The specimen is modelled in the thickness direction (vertical) with one finite element per ply. In order to keep the aspect ratio of the element near unity, the length of the element is set to 0.125 mm, except in the clamped zone of the specimen. This size, comprised in the practical range established by [10], is refined enough to achieve accurate results without increasing excessively the number of elements of the mesh. The clamped zone of the specimen is also modelled with one element per ply in the thickness direction but 1 mm long in the longitudinal direction (horizontal). The interlaminar crack is modelled as a longitudinal discontinuity with different nodes attached to the top and bottom crack surfaces. The nodes at both discontinuity (crack) sides have the same coordinates and are coupled through multi-point constraints. The four MMELS specimens considered in the previous section are modelled taking into account the same material and geometric properties.

Fig. 7: Schema of the VCCT model for the MMELS with centred applied load

The results of the VCCT analysis showing the variation of the energy release rate and mode mix versus crack length for the four specimens with different thickness ratios are summarised in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: Variation of G and G_{II}/G versus a for the VCCT model of the MMELS test

ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

Comparing the results for the variation of the total energy release rate versus the crack length predicted by the three theoretical approaches considered and the results of the VCCT model, it can be observed that the BT, OR and VCCT results are nearly identical for the four thickness ratios taken into account. On the other hand, the variation of G predicted by the CTE/NSF approach differs considerably from the other three.

With respect to the variation of the mode mix, the results for OR and VCCT coincide for the four values of η , while the BT predictions only are coincident with the VCCT results for the specimen with $\eta = 1$. For the rest of the cases, when $\eta < 1$, the variation of the mode mix predicted by the BT is lower than that obtained with the VCCT analysis, especially for long cracks and low values of η . In the case of the specimen with $\eta = 0.25$ and a crack length $a = 100$ mm, the mode mix predicted by the BT approach is 50 times lower than the corresponding VCCT result. Again, the predictions of the CTE/NSF approach differ from the VCCT results, especially when $\eta < 1$, and more if it is taken into account that in this case the predicted mode mix does not depend on the crack extension.

For a quantitative comparison of the three approaches present in the literature with the VCCT results, the averaged sum of the squared residuals of the results is calculated as

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(y_i - y'_i)^2}{n} \quad (7)$$

where the y_i correspond to the values obtained with the VCCT and y'_i are the values calculated with BT, OR or CTE/NSF. The calculated sums of the squared residuals of the total energy release rate and mode mix for the four thickness ratios considered are summarised in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9: χ^2 -values of (a) G and (b) G_{II}/G for the four different thickness ratios

After Fig. 9, it is clear that the OR approach is the one that best coincides with the results obtained with the VCCT analysis of the MMELS test. Consequently, it can be considered that the OR approach is the one that can model the MMELS test more accurately for any value of the thickness ratio η . For the case when $\eta = 1$, BT theory can also model the MMELS test in a correct way. However, for other values of the thickness ratio, the coincidence with the VCCT results in the prediction of G but with different results in the prediction of G_{II}/G reveals that there exist important differences in the mode partitioning of the total energy release rate.

CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, the MMELS test has been analysed by using four different approaches. Two of these approaches, beam theory and orthotropic rescaling, have been already used to model the MMELS test. The formulation of the third approach, the crack tip element/non-singular field, has been employed in this study to analyse the same test. Important differences have been found in the results of the three approaches present in the literature. Consequently, a more accurate alternative analysis of the MMELS test, based on the virtual crack closure technique (VCCT), has been conducted. The comparison between results shows that orthotropic rescaling can model the MMELS test with accuracy, including total energy release rate and mode I, mode II and the mode mix for any value of the thickness ratio. On the other hand, beam theory only is capable of modelling the MMELS test when the thickness ratio is equal to the unity (centred crack). For the rest of the cases, the total energy release rate is predicted correctly but the mode I and mode II components cannot be determined in the correct way. Finally, the predictions of the crack tip element/non-singular field approach differ considerably from the VCCT results and cannot model the variation of G_{II}/G with a .

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